

1	100.1733398	122.2733398
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1.4	100.1733398	122.2733398
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1.55	98.23699951	120.3369995
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1.65	98.23699951	120.3369995
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1.8	98.23699951	120.3369995
1.85	98.23699951	120.3369995
1.9	98.23699951	120.3369995
1.95	98.23699951	120.3369995
2	98.23699951	120.3369995
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2.15	98.23699951	120.3369995
2.2	98.23699951	120.3369995
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2.3	98.23699951	120.3369995
2.35	98.23699951	120.3369995
2.4	98.23699951	120.3369995
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2.5	98.23699951	120.3369995						
2.55	98.23699951	120.3369995						
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2.65	98.23699951	120.3369995						
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2.85	98.23699951	120.3369995						
2.9	98.23699951	120.3369995						
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3.95	96.17156982	118.2715698						

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4.9	94.10614014	116.2061401						
4.95	94.10614014	116.2061401						
5	94.10614014	116.2061401						
5.05	96.17156982	118.2715698						
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5.3	96.17156982	118.2715698						
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5.4	94.10614014	116.2061401						
5.45	94.10614014	116.2061401						

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7.95	94.10614014	116.2061401						
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9.05	93.57820677	115.6782068						
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9.3	93.42485377	115.5248538						
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9.4	93.36351256	115.4635126						
9.45	93.33284196	115.432842						
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